

TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR ON THE BASE OF CORPORA

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Lapasova Obida Abduraimovna

Samarkand city 48th comprehensive school

Research advisor: Maxmudova M.A

Annotation: *Language teaching in the last three decades has focused on the process of learning through communication, with little or no attention to the forms of the language. However valuable this approach, there has been growing recognition that knowledge of the language system and accuracy are also relevant. Teachers' interest in the content of language learning has revived and it is precisely corpora-based research that makes this information available for language teachers and researchers. This article provides some examples of corpora-based works and mentions some advantages of using corpora in the English learning classroom, it reviews several studies that have been carried out on this topic, that explain why using corpora for English Teaching is valuable.*

Keywords: *corpora, advantages, English, teaching.*

Traditional English teaching (emphasizing systemic accuracy) has been all but abandoned for the last three decades and new theories have emerged; language teaching through communication has become popular. The communicative approach to teach English highlights the importance of communicating ideas without worrying about the way they are expressed, that is to say, the message is more important than systemic language accuracy (Kennedy, 1998). Due to the shift in teaching focus, the teachers' role changed as well; in the traditional method teachers were the source of information, while in the communicative approach they became guides, organizers, and knowledge facilitators.

Advantages of using corpora.

Corpora analysis for language teaching and the role it plays in the teaching-learning process has both advantages and disadvantages. This article however is limited to showing some of the advantages of using corpora to inform linguistic practices in the English classroom. It should be noted that the advantages mentioned below are just a small sample of a larger list.

i) Corpora can inform deductive and inductive approaches to English teaching:

In the deductive approach to teaching English, corpora analysis provides evidence that informs teachers (especially to those who are non native speakers)

about the use of language elements they are presenting in class and provides them with clear and authentic examples of the language elements.

In the inductive approach to teaching English, corpora analysis provides students with data to infer language rules by themselves.

j) The use of corpora improves English programs and materials design courses

Gabrielatos (2005) suggests that teachers and material writers may unwittingly present their personal informal observations about language as the true and full picture of language structure and use, or present their own preferred usage as the only 'correct' or 'acceptable' one' (p.5).

However, because corpora informs us about the use of language elements in a way that our intuition cannot, corpora can enlighten the syllabus, and most teaching materials can be based around corpus data. A clear example of this is the use of modals and the form in which they are presented in English textbooks. According to the corpora-based studies on modals (e.g. *would, can, might* etc.) carried out by several researchers (Holmes 1988; Hyland 1994; McEnery & Kifle 2002; Römer 2004) in which they compared how speakers and writers use this language to how textbooks claim students should use it; they found that textbooks are not teaching the full inventory of modal language, they are also providing confusing explanations for some of the language they teach.

Hyland (1994) concludes that for the most part, modal expressions are simply introduced without system or comment and are summarily dealt with in a single exercise

which fails to emphasise either their function or importance. Generally, the range of modal verbs addressed and the information provided on their use is inadequate.... (p. 247).

In the same vein, Williams (1988) affirms that the selection of examples is unclear, but she would suspect that authors too enthusiastically use introspection or a type of educated hunch, instead of an empirical research.

k) Corpora and language awareness

Language awareness can be defined as “the development in learners of an enhanced consciousness of and sensitivity to the forms and functions of the language” (Carter 2003, p. 64). This is why corpora analysis plays an important role in learners language awareness: when students work with corpora they discover language for themselves. Bolitho et al. (2003) state that language discovery is the key element of the language awareness approaches. Van Lier (2001) gives an example of a language awareness teaching activity which shows how the focus is on the learners, not the teacher:

‘...using data provided or collected, learners observe and analyse patterns of interest and come up with descriptions or tentative rules, usually in group work. In most cases the data are from authentic sources.... [...] Teachers can also use concordancers with authentic texts in order to raise awareness of grammatical, stylistic and lexical features....’ (Van Lier, 2001, p.164)

In language learning, reflection and awareness-raising could be associated with 'noticing'. An important function of raising language awareness in the learners is to help them 'notice' the language feature and 'notice the gap' between their own production and the correct grammatical feature as produced by native speakers (Schmidt, 1990). An example of 'noticing' is a class activity Watson Todd (2001) carried out, he identified vocabulary that his Thai students in a pre-intermediate course had problems with in the writing practices, but he didn't correct these problems, just underlined them. He asked learners to search for this vocabulary on the Internet, and to make concordances (10 examples) containing the vocabulary. Then he asked them to find out why they made mistakes by comparing their writing and the concordance sentences, after looking at concordances of the word *capable* a student wrote the next correct rule:

- ✓ *Capable* is used between verb *to be* and *of*
- ✓ *Capable* is always followed by *verb + ing*

This student also corrected his incorrect use of the word *capable* successfully. The results of this English practice was that at the end of the lesson learners were able to notice and self-correct their errors in **over 78%** of cases.

1) Corpora and ELT methodology.

Corpora is normally associated with noticing and language awareness. Gabriellatos (2005) draws attention to the fact that corpora can also be used by teachers following more traditional methodologies, such as PPP (Presentation–Practice–Production), as well as task-based approaches. He argues this because corpora can be used to look up examples of the language the teacher (or the students) wish to focus on, for instance in a PPP lesson, instead of using invented sentences which contain the target language (e.g. *should* and *must*), the teacher could obtain sample sentences containing *should* and *must* from a corpus, then teach the lesson in the typical fashion.

However we should not forget that although corpora can be used to design a more

traditional style of lesson like PPP, corpora use is normally seen by researchers as helping to create a less teacher-centred classroom atmosphere.

Nowadays in a globalized world it is impossible to conceive of education without technology and all the advantages that it has given to the teaching- learning process in general, and to the language teaching-learning process in particular. It is difficult not to realize that computers are used to inform teachers in developing classroom activities as well as to facilitate their job.

The use of corpora is a new tool that provides teachers with authentic data about language structure and also promotes student autonomy because they can explore a determined corpus and do their own research about language features.

Unfortunately, using corpora is not an easy task, especially for those teachers from institutions whose aim is not just English teaching (typical public school with limitations), and therefore therefore it is possible that even when English teachers are informed of this new technology, they may continue to base their teaching on textbooks with dubious language content.

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